

Experimental study on cooling performance of flat heat pipe for lithium-ion battery at various inclination angels

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ABSTRACT

The temperature prediction of lithium-ion battery cells under different working conditions is still a significant challenge. A heat pipe-based air cooling system is presented for thermal management of the lithium-titanite (LTO) cell. Experimental studies are done on the thermal efficiency performance of a flat copper heat pipe on the LTO cell. The effects of the various inclinations (0° to 90°) on the heat pipe resistance are analyzed as well. It was found that increasing the inclination angle of the heat pipe has a critical effect on the cooling process and thermal resistance of the heat pipe since it directly influences the operation of the condensed working fluid. Results indicate that by increasing the inclination angle of heat pipe from 0° to 90° degree, the temperature difference for evaporator and condenser reduced from 5.26°C to 5.04°C , which leads to a thermal resistance reduction of 0.02 K/W . Moreover, the backside temperature of the cell experienced a 1.3°C reduction.

Keywords; Lithium-ion battery; Battery thermal management; Air cooling system; Heat pipe; Inclination angels

1. INTRODUCTION

Lithium-ion (Li-ion) battery cells have received more attention with the development of electric vehicles. They profit from many advantages comprising high specific energy, long cycle life, low self-discharge, and no memory effect [1,2]. However, the performance and thermal safety of the Li-ion cells are strongly temperatures dependent, especially at high current applications [3]. Therefore, preserve the cells within the optimum range of temperature via an efficient battery thermal management system is essential. Many active and passive cooling systems have been used by researchers to control the temperature of the Li-ion cells in the optimum range [4–11]. The air-cooling system is the most common and simplest cooling system, which is used in many cooling applications. However, it is not practical in high current applications due to the lack of heat transfer coefficient of air [12]. Liquid cooling is the most promising cooling system which has a better cooling capacity compared with the air cooling system. Thanks to the higher heat transfer of coefficient and thermal conductivity of the liquid compare with air [13,14]. Nonetheless, heavy components, high cost, and potential leakage problems remain a challenge. Phase change material (PCM) is a passive cooling system that profits from uniform cooling, simple layout, and no power consumption [15,16]. PCM cooling is a new thermal management system (TMS) that is firstly suggested by Al-Hallaj and Selman [17]. PCM can guarantee uniform temperature distribution within the battery; nevertheless, insufficient thermal stability, low thermal conductivity, and limited temperature range of phase change limit their application in battery TMS. The heat pipe has been classified as a superconductor, which shows many advantages in cooling applications [18–20]. It is known as one of the best efficient passive heat transfer tools worldwide. The core structure of a heat pipe is made up of the container, working fluid in both liquid and vapor phases and wick structure. The heat pipe can consistently preserve the evaporator surface at a constant temperature and with high thermal conductivity. Throughout the heat transfer process, the heat flow is conducted to the heat pipe at the evaporation section, which allows the working fluid to evaporate. Heat is transferred due to pressure difference to the condenser section through a vapor line. In the condenser section, the working fluid is condensed due to the heat dissipation. The liquid working fluid returns to the evaporator by capillary wicking structure. The heat pipes benefit from flexible geometry, no maintenance, and a long life span. They are known as a promising candidate for cooling of battery module/pack in electric vehicles. Behi et al. [21] numerically considered the effect of the flat heat pipe with copper sheets (HPCS) for the cylindrical battery module. Tran et al.

[12] experimentally studied the cooling performance of the flat heat pipe for the cylindrical battery module. They found the flat heat pipe is more successful to control the heat flux compared with the conventional heat sink. Wei et al. [22] studied the cooling performance of the oscillating heat pipe with binary-fluid mixtures for electric vehicle thermal management. They could control the maximum temperature of the battery pack below the 45.6 °C in 56W. Liang et al. [23] studied the effect of the heat pipe based thermal management system on a prismatic battery module/pack. Behi et al. [24] experimentally and numerically analyzed the flat heat pipe thermal management system for the cooling application of the prismatic Li-ion cell/module in the high current application.

As it is discussed in literature during the last years, the application of heat pipes for electric vehicle thermal management has been rapidly growing. However, orientation and gravity have a noticeable effect on the performance of the heat pipes. Moving the car in different orientations probably influences the performance of the heat pipe-based cooling system. For this aim, some researchers have studied the effect of gravity on heat pipe thermal performance. Vasilev et al. [25] and Kamotani [26] investigated the influence of inclination angle on the performance of heat pipes. Yousefi et al. [27] experimentally studied the effect of the inclination angle on the heat pipe CPU coolers. They found that the inclination angle of the unit influenced the cooling process since it directly affects the operation of the evaporator. The influence generally returns the capillary effect and boiling limits of the heat pipe. Zhang et al. [28] experimentally investigated the thermal performance of aluminum flat heat pipes in different inclination angles. Ye et al. [29] considered the heat pipe-based cooling system for the fast-charging of Li-ion prismatic battery packs. They studied the operation performance of the heat pipe-based cooling system in the horizontal and vertical axis.

As it is considered in the literature survey, there are a limited number of published papers on the study of inclination angle on the thermal performance of heat pipe for battery cooling. To address this objective, an experimental setup has been developed to investigate the thermal efficiency performance and resistance of a flat copper heat pipe on the LTO cell. Section 2.1 and 2.2 discuss the experimental setup and procedure. In section 3, which is entitled as results and discussions, the experimental data are presented and analyzed. This section provides a discussion of the influence of the inclination angles on thermal management of LTO cell and

thermal resistance of the heat pipe. Lastly, in the conclusion section, a complete assessment of this experimental study is provided.

2. EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Experimental test setup

In the current study, the performance of a heat pipe-based air cooling system has been investigated in different inclination angles. The goal of this design is to consider the effect of heat pipe inclination angles on the thermal management of the LTO cell. The main properties of the heat pipe and the LTO cell are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. The main properties of the heat pipe and Li-ion battery cell

Parameter (Heat-pipe)	Value	Parameter (Li-ion battery cell)	Value
Length (mm)	250	Chemistry	LTO
Dimension L×W (mm)	11.2×3.5	Shape	Prismatic
Working fluid	Distilled water	Nominal Voltage (V)	2.3
Wick structure	Sintered	Weight (kg)	0.550
Thermal conductivity (W/m.K)	8212	Dimensions L×W×H (mm)	115×22×103
Cooling Power (W)	100	Capacity (Ah)	23
Operation temperature (°C)	30- 120	Heat specific capacity (J/kg.K)	1150
Cross-section area (mm ²)	38.32	Thermal conductivity x,y,z (W/m.K)	31, 0.8, 31

The picture of the test setup is shown in Fig. 1a,b. The experimental setup comprised a PEC battery tester, a cooling fan, an anemometer, a flat heat pipe, a prismatic LTO cell, a Pico USB TC-08 data logger, six K-type thermocouples, and a personal computer. The thermocouples with the accuracy of ± 0.2 °C are connected on the surface of the cell and heat pipe. In order to specifically consider the effect of the heat pipe cooling, the cell insulated properly to avoid heat losses by natural air cooling. As it is shown in Fig. 1c the evaporator section of the flat heat pipe is connected to the cell with a length of 115 mm. In order to decrease the thermal contact resistance, a thermal interface material with a thermal conductivity of 8 W/m.K is used between the heat pipe and the cell surface. The rest of the

heat pipe, which is cooled by the fan, is considered as a condenser by the length of the 135 mm.

Fig. 1(a,b). The picture of the experimental setup, and (c) the location of thermocouples

In the current experiment, the PEC battery tester is connected to the cell, and the data-logger measures the temperature of the cell and heat pipe. During the discharging process, the voltage and current of the cell are being monitored. The discharging of the cell is done in high current in which the cell is discharged by the current rate of 8C (184 A) at 446 seconds. The voltage, current, and resistance of the battery cell are characterized by charging/discharging of the cell. The heat generation of the cell can be calculated as follows:

$$q_g = R_{bt} \cdot I^2 = V \cdot I$$

(1)

where R_{bt} , V and I represent the battery resistance, voltage, and current, respectively [30]. It was found that the average heat generation of the cell in the 8C discharging rate is 37.65 W, which is calculated based on equation 1. The ambient temperature of the room keeps

constant at 22 °C. Equation 2 displays the Schultz and Cole [31,32] method to calculate the uncertainty.

$$U_R = \left[\sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial V_i} U_{V_i} \right)^2 \right]^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

Where U_{V_i} and U_R are the error of each factor and total errors respectively. The measurement correctness of each factor is shown in Table 2. The maximum uncertainty is calculated as 2.01%.

Table 2. The uncertainties of the experimental parameters

Parameter	Uncertainty
Current (A)	± 0.1%
Voltage (V)	± 0.1%
Thermocouple (°C)	± 0.2
Data logger (°C)	± 0.025

2.2 Experimental procedure

These experiments were performed to evaluate the performance of the heat pipe-based air cooling system in different inclination angles regarding the thermal resistance of the heat pipe. The cell surface is completely insulated in order to neglect the effect of heat loss by natural convection. First, the LTO cell is discharged at the 8C rate when the heat pipe angle is zero. The temperature of the cell and heat pipe is measured by 6 thermocouples to determine the effect of the heat pipe on the thermal management of the battery cell. In the next steps, the tests are done while the heat pipe angles increased from 0° to 30°, 45°, 60°, and 90° degrees.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Influence of the inclination angles on thermal management of LTO cell

The experimental tests by heat pipe-based air cooling are designed to investigate the cooling effect and thermal performance of the heat pipe on the LTO cell. Due to the high thermal conductivity of the heat pipe, some part of the cell heat generation is quickly absorbed and transfers to the air. Fig. 1c displays the schematic front and backside of the LTO battery cell with the heat pipe and the location of thermocouples. The evaporator section of the heat pipe

is connected to the hottest zone of the cell, and the condenser section is the rest of the heat pipe, which is cooled by forced air cooling with an inlet velocity of 3 m/s [24]. The temperature of the insulated cell and heat pipe is measured in 6 points under the 8C discharging rate. The following tests are done at different heat pipe inclination angles to consider the effect of gravity on heat pipe performance. The distribution curve for the heat pipe in the 0° degree is shown in Fig. 2. There is a meaningful temperature difference among cell temperature, evaporator, and condenser section of the heat pipe. The backside of the cell, evaporator, and condenser average temperature reached 55.2 °C, 48.1 °C, and 42.8 °C, respectively. It is important to note that the average temperature of the cell is lower due to the effect of the heat pipe. Owing to the low number of heat pipes and low thermal conductivity of the cell on the Y-axis, the cooling effect of the heat pipe in the backside is not impressive.

Fig. 2. The inclination angle effect of 0° on thermal management of the LTO cell

The temperature variation in the surface of the cell and heat pipe in 30° degree is shown in Fig. 3. Generally, by increasing the heat pipe angle, the condensed working fluid formed by vapor condensation return to the evaporator through the flow along the cavity wall by gravity and sucked into the wick by the capillary force where the flow speed is closely related to the

capillary performance. It can be seen that the trend of the temperature variations is the same as the 0° degree. The back flow speed is almost not changed for the same wick under 30°-degree inclination angle. The backside of the cell, evaporator, and condenser average temperature reached 54.8 °C, 47.1 °C, and 41.9 °C, respectively. It is evident due to the effect of gravity, the backside of the cell, evaporator, and average condenser temperature decreased by 0.4 °C, 1 °C, and 0.9 °C, respectively.

Fig. 3. The inclination angle effect of 30° on thermal management of the LTO cell

Fig. 4 displays the temperature rise distribution curve for the heat pipe in 45° degree. Under inclination of 45° degree, the gravity can increase the speed of the liquid working fluid while the wick structure remains the same. The gravity does not affect the trend of the temperature variations for 45° degrees. The backside of the cell, evaporator, and condenser average temperature reached 54.4 °C, 46.12 °C, and 40.9 °C, respectively. It is obvious due to the effect of gravity and compares with the 0° degree, the backside of the cell, evaporator, and average condenser temperature decreased by 0.8 °C, 1.98 °C, and 1.9 °C, respectively.

Fig. 4. The inclination angle effect of 45° on thermal management of the LTO cell

Fig. 5 shows the variation of the temperature curves of cell and heat pipe in 60° degree inclination. The trend of the temperature variations is the same as other inclination angles. The backside of the cell, evaporator, and condenser average temperature reached 54.3 °C, 46 °C, and 40.9 °C, respectively. It is clear the gravity does not change the temperatures and compares with the 45° degree. The backside of the cell, evaporator, and average condenser temperature compares with 0° degree decreased by 0.9 °C, 2.1 °C, and 1.9 °C, respectively.

Fig. 5. The inclination angle effect of 60° on thermal management of the LTO cell

Fig. 6 shows the inclination of 90° degree, which tests the heat pipe vertically. The heat pipe presents the optimal thermal performance for the inclination angle of 90° degree, with a minimum temperature difference between the condenser and evaporator and minimum cell temperature due to the fastest liquid replenishment. The backside of the cell, evaporator, and condenser average temperature reached 53.9 °C, 45.7 °C, and 40.7 °C, respectively. The backside of the cell, evaporator, and average condenser temperature compares with 0° degree decreased by 1.3 °C, 2.4 °C, and 2.1 °C, respectively.

Fig. 6. The inclination angle effect of 90° on thermal management of the LTO cell

3.2 Influence of the inclination angles on the thermal resistance of heat pipe

The thermal resistance of the heat pipe can be calculated by equation 3.

$$R = \frac{(T_e - T_c)}{Q} \quad (3)$$

where T_e and T_c are the average temperature values at condenser and evaporator, respectively. Moreover, Q is the heat supplied to the heat pipe. Fig. 7a shows the effect of different heat pipe inclination angles on the thermal resistance of the heat pipe. It can be seen the thermal resistance of the heat pipe decreases by increasing the angle from 0° to 90° degree. In this study, gravity, despite the capillary force, helps the condensed working fluid flow back faster to the evaporator. Therefore, the backflow speed increases, which can reduce the thermal resistance of the heat pipe. It is important to note that increasing the angle of the heat pipe is not always efficient, and it is related to the type of wick structure, working fluid, and amount of filling ratio. Moreover, in this study, in negative angles (0° to -90°), gravity acts as a destructive item, which increases the thermal resistance of the heat pipe.

Fig. 7. The effect of inclination angles, (a) on the thermal resistance of heat pipe, (b), and temperature difference of evaporator and condenser.

Fig.7b shows the temperature difference between evaporator and condenser sections under different inclination angles. As it is obvious by increasing inclination angles, the temperature difference between the evaporator and condenser sections decreases. According to equation 3, as the temperature difference decrease, the thermal resistance reduces as well. By increasing the inclination angle from 0° to 90° degree, the condensed working fluid can positively flow backward to the evaporator section owing to the gravity force, which leads to smaller flow resistance for working fluid circulation.

4. CONCLUSION

Experimental tests are developed to investigate the effect of inclination angles on the heat pipe thermal management and resistance performance. It was found that the performance of a heat pipe used for thermal management of the LTO cell is significantly affected by the orientation angle of the unit. The condensed working fluid, by increasing the inclination angle, can ideally return faster to the evaporator section due to the gravity force, which leads to smaller flow resistance for working fluid circulation. Experimental results proved that by increasing the inclination angle of heat pipe from 0° to 90° degree, the temperature difference for evaporator and condenser decreased from 5.26 °C to 5.04 °C, which cause a thermal resistance reduction of 0.02 K/W. Additionally, the backside temperature of the cell experienced a 1.3 °C reduction.

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